

AOPGraphExplorer 2.0: An Integrated Graph-Based Platform for Multi-Domain Annotation and Visualization of Adverse Outcome Pathways

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Abstract

The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework is a cornerstone in mechanistic toxicology, linking molecular initiating events to adverse biological outcomes. Yet, the increasing complexity and fragmentation of AOP-related data across multiple resources hinder efficient exploration and mechanistic interpretation.

Here, we present AOPGraphExplorer 2.0, an integrated graph platform that enables the interactive visualization, annotation, and analysis of AOP networks derived from AOPWiki. The new version introduces seamless integration of multi-domain annotation sources, allowing users to enrich AOP networks with pathway, disease, and tissue-specific information. This integration facilitates a deeper understanding of how molecular perturbations propagate across biological systems to drive toxicological and pathological outcomes.

AOPGraphExplorer 2.0 provides instant, graph-based visualizations with exportable HTML and JSON formats for documentation, sharing, and computational reuse. It also delivers quantitative network statistics, summarizing nodes, edges, AOPs, stressors, and annotation coverage, alongside evidence-based filtering of Key Events (KEs) by confidence and quantitative understanding scores.

By bridging AOPWiki with external biomedical knowledge, AOPGraphExplorer 2.0 transforms AOP exploration into a multi-domain network analysis process, advancing the integration of systems toxicology, pharmacology, and disease biology. This user-friendly, open-access platform supports hypothesis generation, data interpretation, and evidence-based decision-making, accelerating research in drug safety, environmental health, and risk assessment.